

DO ETHICAL RULES NEED TO CHANGE OVER TIME? A LOOK AT PROFESSIONAL CODES OF ETHICS

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Abstract

Ethical rules change over time. Various accounting and other professional groups have changed their codes of ethics to meet changing circumstances and conditions. But do these ethical rules change because times have changed, or have they changed because the older codes of ethics were defective ab initio and needed to be changed to correct defects? This article discusses the reasons why some codes of ethics have changed and concludes that fewer changes would have been needed if the codes had not been defective in the first place. The author also makes some suggestions for improving existing codes of ethics.

Introduction

There is an age-old debate about whether ethical principles are etched in stone or whether they need to change with the times. I do not intend to get into that debate or even to refer to any of the vast literature that has been written on this point going back as far as Plato and Aristotle. I would merely like to make a few points about why the various accounting and legal codes of ethics have

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changed in recent decades and perhaps find an explanation for the changes. I would also like to suggest a few changes that should be made to existing codes of ethics to make them more ethical.

Ethical Rules

Ethics has been defined as the study of morality.² It has also been defined as a theory or system of moral values.³ Both of these definitions lead one to ask another question: What is morality or what are moral values?

We can agree on many moral values. Values such as thou shalt not kill, thou shalt not steal, and so forth have existed for thousands of years across a wide range of cultures, religions and geographic locations. Almost everyone except serial killers can agree that these are ethical values that should be recognized and practiced.⁴

Other practices that are viewed as ethical or unethical are not so clear-cut. Is it ethical to eat pork? Is it ethical to eat meat along with dairy products? Is it ethical to eat meat on Friday?⁵ Is it

² MARY BETH ARMSTRONG, *ETHICS AND PROFESSIONALISM FOR CPAS* 2 (Cincinnati: South-Western Publishing Company, 1993).

³ Gordon M. Cohn, *Accounting Ethics and the Traditional Jewish Perspective*, in W. MICHAEL HOFFMAN, JUDITH BROWN KAMM, ROBERT E. FREDERICK AND EDWARD S. PETRY, EDITORS, *THE ETHICS OF ACCOUNTING & FINANCE: TRUST, RESPONSIBILITY, AND CONTROL* 180-190 (Westport, CT: Quorum Books, 1996), at 180.

⁴ It should be noted that just because some vast majority thinks something is moral (or immoral) does not make it so. Majoritarianism has nothing to do with morality. Right is right and wrong is wrong regardless of votes or majority rule. Slavery was once considered to be a moral institution, even instituted by God. Vast majorities thought so. People quoted the Bible to prove their point. We now recognize that owning another person is immoral. That is not to say that moral rules have changed; it is just that we have discovered rules that have always existed.

⁵ The present author once thought that one would go to hell for eternity for eating meat on Friday because that is what the nuns and priests told me when I attended Catholic schools. I was also told that this rule applied only to Catholics. Noncatholics were off the hook in this regard.

ethical to eat meat at all? Millions of people can be found on both sides of these issues.

Ethics or morality can also be divided into two broad categories: actions that affect others and actions that don't. Actions that affect others include murder and theft. Actions that do not affect others include masturbation and having sex with dead animals. Many people think that masturbation is wrong. Some sociologists, psychologists and at least one former Surgeon General of the United States think that it is beneficial, at least sometimes.⁶ Most people would agree that the very thought of having sex with a dead animal is disgusting. Yet it is a religious practice in some parts of the world.⁷

A distinction also needs to be made between unethical actions that need to be punished and those that do not require punishment. This latter category could be called victimless crimes. Such "crimes" include any contract entered into by consenting adults, such as ticket scalping, polygamy, dwarf tossing,⁸ prostitution and the purchase and sale of drugs.⁹ Perhaps these activities are unethical and perhaps they are not, but it is beyond the legitimate scope of government to punish people who do not violate the rights of others. If governments have any legitimate

⁶ One former Surgeon General of the United States suggested that masturbation be taught in the schools. With such great advice as this, one wonders whether we need a Surgeon General. There is nothing in the U.S. Constitution that permits such an office to exist. However, any further discussion of this point would take us too far afield of the present topic.

⁷ Haiti is one country that comes to mind in this regard but there are probably others.

⁸ For a discussion of the sport of dwarf tossing from a property rights perspective, see Robert W. McGee, *If Dwarf Tossing Is Outlawed, Only Outlaws Will Toss Dwarfs: Is Dwarf Tossing a Victimless Crime?* 38 AMERICAN JOURNAL OF JURISPRUDENCE 335-358 (1993).

⁹ For discussions about victimless crimes, see PETER MCWILLIAMS, *AIN'T NOBODY'S BUSINESS IF YOU DO: THE ABSURDITY OF CONSENSUAL CRIMES IN OUR FREE COUNTRY* (Los Angeles: Prelude Press, 1996); JOEL FEINBERG, *HARMLESS WRONGDOING: THE MORAL LIMITS OF THE CRIMINAL LAW* (New York: Oxford University Press, 1990).

functions at all, it is to protect rights, like the rights to life, liberty and property. Protecting the rights to contract and associate (or not associate)¹⁰ also fall within the legitimate scope of governments. Indeed, that is the reason why governments are formed, to protect these rights. Any code of ethics that would punish individuals for committing victimless crimes is defective.¹¹ Any code of ethics that would punish individuals for doing something that is not unethical is also defective.¹² Any code of ethics that protects the members of some profession at the expense of the general public is also defective and needs to be changed.¹³ One might add that it is also improper for a code of ethics to punish someone for doing something that has nothing to do with the practice of the profession in question, even if the action might be unethical or in violation of someone's rights.¹⁴

¹⁰ For a discussion of the right not to associate, see Robert W. McGee, *The Right Not To Associate: The Case for an Absolute Freedom of Negative Association*, 23 UNIVERSITY OF WEST LOS ANGELES LAW REVIEW 123-148 (1992).

¹¹ For more on this point, see Robert W. McGee, *Can Sexual Acts between (or among) Consenting Adults be Considered an Act Discreditable to the Profession under AICPA Code of Professional Conduct Rule 501? A Philosophical Look at a Practical Ethical Question*, 2 JOURNAL OF ACCOUNTING, ETHICS & PUBLIC POLICY (Fall 1999).

¹² For more on this point, see Robert W. McGee, *Should Accountants be Punished for Aiding and Abetting Tax Evasion?* 1 JOURNAL OF ACCOUNTING, ETHICS & PUBLIC POLICY 16-44 (Winter 1998); Robert W. McGee, *When Is Tax Evasion Unethical?* in ROBERT W. MCGEE, EDITOR, *THE ETHICS OF TAX EVASION* 5-35 (South Orange, NJ: The Dumont Institute, 1998); Robert W. McGee, *Advertising and Solicitation: Some Ethical Problems with the IFAC Code of Ethics*, 1 JOURNAL OF ACCOUNTING, ETHICS & PUBLIC POLICY (Spring 1998).

¹³ For more on this point, see Robert W. McGee, *Advertising and Solicitation: Some Ethical Problems with the IFAC Code of Ethics*, 1 JOURNAL OF ACCOUNTING, ETHICS & PUBLIC POLICY (Spring 1998).

¹⁴ For more on this point, see Robert W. McGee, *Should Sexual Harassment Constitute an Act Discreditable to the Profession? A Philosophical Look at a Practical Ethical Question*, 2 JOURNAL OF ACCOUNTING, ETHICS & PUBLIC POLICY (Spring 1999); Robert W. McGee, *Should Rule 501 (Acts Discreditable)*

How Have Prior Codes of Ethics Been Defective?

Prior codes of ethics have been defective because they have either punished individuals for conduct that does not violate anyone's rights¹⁵ or they have been self-serving,¹⁶ offering protection to the profession at the expense of the general public. Let's take an example from an AICPA¹⁷ publication.

of the AICPA Code of Professional Conduct be Repealed? A Philosophical Look at a Practical Ethical Question, 2 JOURNAL OF ACCOUNTING, ETHICS & PUBLIC POLICY (Summer 1999); Robert W. McGee, *What Constitutes an Act Discreditable to the Profession? A Philosophical Look at a Practical Ethical Question*, 2 JOURNAL OF ACCOUNTING, ETHICS & PUBLIC POLICY (Winter 1999); Robert W. McGee, *Should Private Discrimination Constitute an Act Discreditable to the Profession? A Philosophical Look at a Practical Ethical Question*, 1 JOURNAL OF ACCOUNTING, ETHICS & PUBLIC POLICY (Fall 1998).

¹⁵ For more on this point, see Robert W. McGee, *Codes of Ethics Can Be Unethical*, 1 JOURNAL OF ACCOUNTING, ETHICS & PUBLIC POLICY (Spring 1998). I deliberately avoided the use of the word "harm" for a very good reason. There is a difference between harming someone and violating his rights. For example, if an accountant harms a fellow practitioner by underbidding on a contract, the accountant who loses the contract may be harmed, but he does not have his rights violated. That is because there is no right to enter into a contract with someone who prefers to enter into a contract with another accountant. Accountants, or anyone for that matter, should not be punished just because they harm someone. They should be punished only if they violate someone's rights. For a discussion of what constitute legitimate rights, see TIBOR MACHAN, *INDIVIDUALS AND THEIR RIGHTS* (LaSalle, IL: Open Court Publishing Company, 1989).

¹⁶ A study of the Australian accounting profession spanning nearly 100 years found that most ethical pronouncements and debates had the primary rationale of protecting the profession rather than the general public. L.D. Parker, *An Historical Analysis of Ethical Pronouncements and Debate in the Australian Accounting Profession*, ABACUS 126-140 (1987), as cited in Lee D. Parker, *Professional Accounting Body Ethics: In Search of the Private Interest*, 19 ACCOUNTING, ORGANIZATIONS AND SOCIETY 507-525 (1994), at 507.

¹⁷ American Institute of Certified Public Accountants.

The word "ethics" in general usage means the philosophy of human conduct with emphasis on "right" and "wrong," which are moral questions.

"Professional ethics," however, does not involve moral questions exclusively. There is nothing immoral, for example, in truthful advertising, but it is unethical for physicians, lawyers and certified public accountants to advertise their professional services, no matter how truthfully.¹⁸

It is no longer considered unethical for physicians, lawyers and accountants to advertise and various codes of ethics have been changed to reflect this new viewpoint.¹⁹ The big question is: Was it ever unethical to advertise? The answer is "no." The ban on advertising in the codes of ethics of the various professions was extremely self-serving and against the public interest. Bans on advertising prevent competition. The bans helped the large, established firms and practitioners at the expense of the smaller and younger practitioners. These bans on advertising were overturned not because the vanguard of the various professions like the AICPA, American Bar Association and American Medical Association "saw the light." They were overturned because practitioners in these fields took them to court to defend their rights to free press and free speech.²⁰

¹⁸ JOHN L. CAREY AND WILLIAM O. DOHERTY, *ETHICAL STANDARDS OF THE ACCOUNTING PROFESSION* 5-6 (New York: American Institute of Certified Public Accountants, 1966).

¹⁹ For a discussion on this point, see Robert W. McGee, *Advertising and Solicitation: Some Ethical Problems with the IFAC Code of Ethics*, 1 *JOURNAL OF ACCOUNTING, ETHICS & PUBLIC POLICY* (Spring 1998).

²⁰ For a listing and brief discussion of some of these cases, see DENZIL Y. CAUSEY, JR. AND SANDRA A. CAUSEY, *DUTIES AND LIABILITIES OF PUBLIC ACCOUNTANTS*, 5th edition 85-6 (Mississippi State, MS: Accountant's Press, 1995).

Bans on advertising are prima facie violations of the rights of free speech and free press. There is no way to ban, prohibit or regulate truthful advertising without also violating individual rights. Before the AICPA changed its rule on advertising, it was considered unethical to have "CPA" listed on an automobile license plate²¹ or to have "CPA" printed on personal checks if the checking account was joint.²² A CPA who was also a bank officer and director could not have CPA listed after his name in the bank's annual report.²³ A CPA could not permit his name to be listed in a directory of specialists.²⁴ CPAs could not even pay to have themselves listed as an accountant in a fraternity directory.²⁵ A CPA who is also a tax attorney could not be listed in a telephone directory as a tax attorney.²⁶

A member of the American Institute of Certified Public Accountants could not mention his AICPA membership in a directory listing because such a designation would tend to differentiate AICPA members from others listed in the directory.²⁷ Help wanted ads could not be in the form of display advertising where a member's name appeared anywhere in the ad.²⁸ CPAs were prohibited from placing "situation wanted" ads.²⁹ CPAs could not list their qualification as an addendum to a report because it would violate the rule prohibiting advertising one's professional attainments.³⁰ It once was considered unethical for a

²¹ CAREY AND DOHERTY, at 217.

²² CAREY AND DOHERTY, at 218.

²³ CAREY AND DOHERTY, at 219.

²⁴ CAREY AND DOHERTY, at 219.

²⁵ CAREY AND DOHERTY, at 220.

²⁶ CAREY AND DOHERTY, at 221-222.

²⁷ CAREY AND DOHERTY, at 223.

²⁸ CAREY AND DOHERTY, at 225.

²⁹ CAREY AND DOHERTY, at 226.

³⁰ CAREY AND DOHERTY, at 227-228.

CPA to appear on television to affirm statements that do not require auditing or other technical work.³¹

There was never anything unethical about any of these things. They were merely classified as unethical and therefore prohibited. Today such prohibitions appear to be ridiculous. But not too long ago accountants had to go to court, often at great expense, to defend their rights to merely disclose the truth.

Solicitation was also prohibited. AICPA's former Rule 3.02 stated: "A member or associate shall not endeavor, directly or indirectly, to obtain clients by solicitation."³²

If a professional man solicits an engagement, he places himself in a position psychologically inferior to that of the prospective client. In view of the CPA's responsibility to the public, as well as to his client, it is desirable that he and his client be on terms of equality.³³

What does "the public" have to do with any of this? If anything, the public benefits from solicitation because solicitation allows information regarding available services and prices to become known where they otherwise would not be known.

At one time it was considered unethical for a CPA to use his letterhead to solicit charitable contributions from anyone other than fellow CPAs.³⁴ A CPA could not offer in a church bulletin to prepare free tax returns for people who contributed to the church.³⁵ If a CPA asks a trade association if he can give a speech, it might have been in violation of the solicitation or advertising rules at one time.³⁶

³¹ CAREY AND DOHERTY, at 229.

³² CAREY AND DOHERTY, at 53.

³³ CAREY AND DOHERTY, at 53.

³⁴ CAREY AND DOHERTY, at 287.

³⁵ CAREY AND DOHERTY, at 290.

³⁶ CAREY AND DOHERTY, at 293-4.

The rules against encroachment were also extremely self-serving. How any educated person could say that such practices were not self-serving is almost beyond comprehension. Yet not too long ago accountants could lose their license to practice if they "encroached" on the practice of another accountant.

Encroachment really means competing for business. AICPA's former Rule 5.01, which prohibited encroachment, stated

A member or associate shall not encroach upon the practice of another public accountant. A member or associate may furnish service to those who request it.³⁷

Carey and Doherty go on to say:

A major purpose of this rule is obviously to preserve harmony within the profession. There is nothing which so disturbs a professional man as to find that his client has been approached by another. This irritation does not spring entirely from mercenary motives. It comes also from hurt pride, and is the more disturbing therefor. The relations between a CPA and his client are personal and friendly, based on mutual confidence and respect. The interloper who tries to break such a relationship, and supplant the CPA who enjoys it, may be sure of the latter's unfriendly reaction.

Encroachment causes enmity, and the organized profession is fully justified in stamping it out in the interests of the group as a whole.³⁸

This statement clearly reveals the self-serving nature of the prohibition on encroachment. The prohibition was clearly aimed at

³⁷ CAREY AND DOHERTY, at 152.

³⁸ CAREY AND DOHERTY, at 152.

promoting self-interest at the expense of the general public, who stand to gain by aggressive competition for their business. Yet CPAs who attempt to serve the public in this manner stood to lose their license to practice, and therefore their livelihood. What is ethical about causing that to happen?

Another extremely self-serving rule was the prohibition on making an offer of employment to someone who worked for another CPA. Former Rule 5.03 stated:

Direct or indirect offer of employment shall not be made by a member or associate to an employee of another public accountant without first informing such accountant. This rule shall not be construed so as to inhibit negotiations with anyone who of his own initiative or in response to public advertisement shall apply to a member or associate for employment.³⁹

Such a rule surely put a chilling effect on employee mobility and advancement, since individuals risked losing their jobs if they dared to apply for a position with another firm. Carey and Doherty explain away this chilling effect by saying that it is "a principle of common courtesy and fair dealing..."⁴⁰ They even go so far as to say that not first notifying the present employer amounts to deception.⁴¹ The self-serving nature of Rule 5.03 is highlighted by the following quote:

It [Rule 5.03] is intended to avoid ill will among members of the profession, and then to strengthen its unity. The rule is also intended to warn the occasional less scrupulous practitioner that he may not with impunity try to lure staff assistants from

³⁹ CAREY AND DOHERTY, at 153-4.

⁴⁰ CAREY AND DOHERTY, at 154.

⁴¹ CAREY AND DOHERTY, at 154.

their present employers who may have taught them all that now makes them valuable.⁴²

While preventing ill will among members is always a good idea, it should not be done at the expense of job advancement and mobility. The unity of the profession here is strengthened by engaging in anticompetitive practices.

Some codes of ethics have even gone so far as to punish members for saying uncomplimentary things about colleagues.⁴³ I fail to see what such prohibitions have to do with ethics although it is clear that such rules totally disregard the right of free speech. Were it not for lawsuits or the threat of lawsuits to protect the rights of free speech and press, it is likely that these restrictive rules would still be included in codes of ethics in the United States. Unfortunately for the accountants who live in countries where such rights are not enshrined in constitutions, such rules sometimes still exist.⁴⁴

Suggestions for Improvement to Existing Codes of Ethics

Many of the unethical provisions of the AICPA's Code of Professional Conduct and the various State codes of ethics in the USA have been repealed, either as a result of litigation or the threat of litigation. However, a few problems remain, as we shall discuss below. Some codes of ethics in other countries have not yet gone through the process of removing unethical sections from their codes of ethics, so this task will have to be completed, the sooner the better.

⁴² CAREY AND DOHERTY, at 155.

⁴³ John W. Cook, *Additional Rules of Professional Ethics*, JOURNAL OF ACCOUNTANCY, February, 1964, page 45, as cited in CAREY AND DOHERTY at 156.

⁴⁴ For example, see Robert W. McGee, *Advertising and Solicitation: Some Ethical Problems with the IFAC Code of Ethics*, 1 JOURNAL OF ACCOUNTING, ETHICS & PUBLIC POLICY (Spring 1998); Robert W. McGee, *Codes of Ethics Can be Unethical*, 1 JOURNAL OF ACCOUNTING, ETHICS & PUBLIC POLICY (Spring 1998).

The general rule to follow when trying to determine which ethical code provisions need to be removed is quite simple. Remove any provision that violates any individual's rights. One might also add that any provisions that are self-serving should be removed, although self-serving provisions generally also violate individual rights. The top four candidates for removal from codes of ethics are any provisions that restrict truthful advertising, solicitation or encroachment or that punish people for doing things that supposedly "discredit" the profession.

Encroachment often means nothing more than rigorous competition. Such competition is good for consumers and any restriction on competition must necessarily violate someone's right to enter into contract, exercise free speech or press, exchange property or associate. Unless encroachment violates someone's negative rights, there is no need to have any restrictions on it. Indeed, restrictions on competition may be presumed to be unethical.⁴⁵

Any restriction on advertising or solicitation must also be removed from codes of ethics. The IFAC Code of Ethics would place restrictions on such activity. The IFAC provision on this topic is blatantly self-serving and protectionist. It is anticompetitive and serves the private interests of accountants at the expense of the general public.⁴⁶ Any country that is thinking of adopting the IFAC Code of Ethics must remove this provision before adoption. Those countries or private associations that have already adopted the IFAC provision that deals with advertising and solicitation should remove them at once, since the IFAC provision is itself unethical.

A number of provisions place a chilling effect on the freedoms of speech and press. Perhaps one of the most self-

⁴⁵ For a discussion of commerce and morality, see TIBOR MACHAN, EDITOR, *COMMERCE AND MORALITY* (Totowa, NJ: Rowman & Littlefield, 1988).

⁴⁶ For more on this point, see Robert W. McGee, *Advertising and Solicitation: Some Ethical Problems with the IFAC Code of Ethics*, 1 *JOURNAL OF ACCOUNTING, ETHICS & PUBLIC POLICY* (Spring 1998).

serving restrictions is the prohibition on making comparisons to other accountants in public practice.⁴⁷ This provision has nothing to do with the public interest. It is about protection. Comparing your prices to those of your competitors would seem like valuable information. However, the IFAC would punish anyone who compared prices. How is the public interest served by such a provision? Newspaper advertising is also prohibited at times.⁴⁸

Another IFAC rule requires that advertising be in good taste⁴⁹ or professionally dignified.⁵⁰ There is not necessarily anything ethically improper about not being in good taste or dignified, yet the IFAC code of "ethics" would sanction individuals for such activity. Yet advertising that is not in good taste or dignified is often the most effective kind of advertising. At the very least it is entertaining.

Concluding Comments

Codes of ethics have gotten better in recent years, but not always for the right reasons. Some unethical provisions have been removed because of court cases or the threat of litigation rather than because those in charge of amending the various ethical codes determined that the provisions violated rights. Codes of ethics have had to be changed in the past because some of their provisions were unethical. Had these codes been completely ethical in the first place, there would have been no need to change anything.

As emerging economies and other countries adopt codes of ethics for the first time, they should look carefully at each and every provision to ensure that the provisions they are adopting are not unethical. Those countries that already have adopted a code of ethics for accounting or for other professions should review what they have adopted and repeal any provision that violates individual

⁴⁷ INTERNATIONAL FEDERATION OF ACCOUNTANTS, IFAC HANDBOOK 1998: TECHNICAL PRONOUNCEMENTS (New York: IFAC, 1998), Sec. 14.3(d).

⁴⁸ Sec. 14.4

⁴⁹ Sec. 14.7(b).

⁵⁰ Sec. 14.7(c).

rights or that serves the membership at the expense of the general public.

Whether ethics change over time or whether ethics is changeless and eternal is a question that we will leave for another day. However, after reviewing the changes that have taken place in professional codes of ethics in recent decades it is clear that codes of ethics need to change, not because ethics have changed but because the codes of ethics were defective and in need of correction.